

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INTERPRETATION OF THE "TEACHING STRATEGIES BLOCK ELEMENTS" OF THE SUBJECT CURRICULUM AT THE GENERAL EDUCATION LEVEL BASED ON THE "SYSTEM-STRUCTURE" APPROACH

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Abstract

The article emphasizes that the curriculum reform is conditioned by the need to ensure the adequacy of the implementation of education in Azerbaijan to the challenges of the 21st century, to cultivate a creative, self-developing personality, and the content of the abilities necessary to become the subject of a student who has completed his general education is shown.

The importance of the educator's reference to the "system-structure" approach in the research work, both in familiarizing himself with the essence of the "General Education Program" and in his practical activities related to its implementation, by covering the field of science related to the content of technical curricula, and its perfect system of concepts, is directly related to these concepts. It is drawn to the center of attention directed to its absorption.

The article presents the interpretation of the generalizations adequately made on the basis of the "system-structure" dialectical approach, which aims to reveal the nature of the sub-systems in order to benefit the educator at the desired level from the following issues, which are included in the "Teaching strategies" block of the "block-scheme" form of the subject curriculum structure at the general education level. : 1) principles of the pedagogical process, 2) planning of training on the subject, 3) forms and methods used in the organization of training, 4) comments and instructions regarding content standards.

Keywords: educational program; curriculum; completeness; supportive environment; unit of study, research question; motivation, reflection; work with groups; creative application.

Relevance of the research topic. Observations show that mistakes are made in the activities of educators in the application of the subject curriculum at the general education level. This has a negative effect on the efficiency level of the subject teaching process.

It is undeniable that the level of understanding of any real existence (objective existence) has a determining effect on the results of using it in adequate directions. On the basis of our scientific observations over the last ten years (at the stage of applying a new approach to the philosophy of general education in Azerbaijan), we have come to the conclusion that one of the main reasons for the mistakes manifested in the activities of educators in the process of using the subject curriculum is that these subjects do not have a sufficiently honest understanding of the essence of the subject curriculum. The "system-structure" approach - the idea of L. Bertalanf [14;6]), which is the basis of system analysis, is the most reliable dialectical method of understanding any objective reality (material or spiritual), to get to its essence, in other words, it is a way of moral exploration. It is essentially a form of cognitive action. The analysis of the materials we have collected gives reason to say that this method is insufficiently used in the theoretical and technological directions of revealing the essence of the subject curriculum and determining

the ways of its application. Therefore, we recommend that only one of the many issues aimed at solving the problem that created the basis for the manifestation of the above-mentioned error - "Interpretation of the "Teaching strategies" block elements" of the subject curriculum at the general education level on the basis of the "system-structure" approach" and that it be an actual research topic we claim.

Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of research materials. It is known that "in the 21st century, the main value in the life and development of both society and each of its members is a creative, self-developing personality" [15; 16] and there is also the fact that education cannot exist outside the realities of a changing world.[11]. "Revealing the child's creative abilities and realizing them, creating favorable conditions for the formation of his personality is one of the main goals of education." [7; 290-292] There is no doubt that subjects, which are the main enabling components of the implementation of general education, are of high value as an important tool in the formation of the personality of schoolchildren. The "enabling" functions of the subjects are expressed in the following content in the Education Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan:

- It ensures that students are taught the basics of science, inculcated the necessary knowledge, skills and habits, and prepare them for life and work;

- It provides an opportunity for the physical and intellectual development of students, acquisition of necessary knowledge, the formation of civic thinking based on a healthy lifestyle and civilized values, instilling a sense of respect for national and worldly values, and determining their rights and responsibilities in front of family, society, the state and the environment. [2;21-23]

Based on the official state documents, we can say that "the content of general education subjects aims at the following hierarchical goals by dividing them into different levels of education":

- to overcome reading, writing and calculation skills in primary education, to form basic knowledge about man, society and nature, elements of logical thinking, aesthetic and artistic taste and other characteristics;

- to evaluate oral speech and writing culture, communication skills, cognitive activity, development of logical thinking, the formation of relevant knowledge and ideas about the subjects included in the educational program as well as the development of world civilization, the ability to use modern information and communication tools, events and provide the ability to determine their future directions of action;

-realization of talents and abilities, preparation for independent life and professional choice, formation of an active citizen position, respect for national and universal values, human rights and freedoms and tolerance, free use of modern information and communication technologies and other technical means, acquiring the basics of economic knowledge, communicating in one or more foreign languages, etc. ensure. (for more details see: [2])

In our opinion, it is of particular importance for the subject teacher to honestly know the tasks set before the general education (general expected results). This is necessary to put the activity related to the educational process into a result-oriented system. As is known, the goal is a system-creative component in all processes, as well as in training activities. In addition, in order to achieve the goal (otherwise, the result will not be achieved), it is very important to implement the training process in what content, based on what strategy, based on what assessment mechanisms. "The new necessary minimum of training at the levels of general education, the knowledge threshold, the general training results for the subject and the training results that will be obtained in advance of the acquired skills at individual levels of general education (subsystems of the implementation system of general education) (which these results are in the expected general results is included as components) is considered one of the most important problems of education". [12;71]

As is known, the teacher should be able to find both theoretical and practical answers to all questions related to the learning process. He should know which model he uses in the process of which he is a facilitator and what specific features this model has. This model incorporates the superior merits of traditional models

(it should not be forgotten that innovation is not a complete denial of the old, such a denial can bring more harm than good) and what success it promises to the real pedagogical process.

Based on what we have said, we summarize that the main features of the educational program (curriculum), which is currently applied in general education schools, "which is perceived as a conceptual document that enables the effective organization of all activities related to the educational process, purposeful and consistent implementation" [8;228-229] It would be beneficial for the overall work to give an interpretation based on the "system-structure" approach.

The teacher is one of the main subjects in the implementation of the educational program. The level of his penetration into the essence of the mentioned program has a conditioning effect on the effectiveness of its activity. Therefore, it is important to refer to the "system-structure" approach both in familiarization with the essence of the program and in the practical activities related to its implementation, which brings us to this conclusion by the analysis of research materials and our work experience.

It should be emphasized here that the essence of the system is determined by its structure and function, that is, by the nature of the relationship between the elements and their behavior, and by the specificity of the relationship between the object and the conditions. Without studying the elements that make up the system and their interaction, it is impossible to distinguish the continuous, important and necessary relationships here. Such continuous, important and necessary interaction of elements characterizes the structure of the system. The law of relationships of structural elements acts as an invariant of the system. Without learning and opening the relationship of the elements with the whole formed by them, both the function of the system and the functions of each element with regard to the whole remain in the shadows. The full concept is understood in terms of the system, it is the organization of that system. Each system has its own structure and the function that this structure carries. A system can be viewed as a whole consisting of the unity of its structure and function. Systems differ from each other not only by their structure and functions, but also mainly by the nature of the unity of structure and function, the nature of this unity.

The educational program (curriculum) determines the content of education and the rules of mastering it at different levels and levels of education in accordance with the state educational standards. [9; 106-107] The educational program includes the curriculum, educational programs for subjects, recommendations on methodical provision, assessment and other relevant educational technologies. [8;173] Listed are subsystems of the Education program - complete.

By the way, let's emphasize that Educational programs (curriculums) are divided into two parts according to their nature: productive and personality oriented. "Personality-oriented", "pupil-oriented" and "result-oriented" approaches of the curriculum show that the student is at the center of the learning process. [11] These approaches are reflected, in particular, in the

writing of learning objectives. The highlighted features of the curriculum have a great benefit in the educational process: it makes the educational process more efficient, it enables the formation of practical skills. In this regard, new demands are placed on the teacher. [3; 174] Subject curricula: take a balanced and comprehensive approach to learning different skills; enables achievement of content standards using active learning methods; implies constant assessment of students'

knowledge and understanding, making corrections during the academic year; ensures involvement of students in training, preparation and motivation for continuous education; it envisages the use of modern technologies while studying, evaluating students' knowledge, improving their literacy; has appropriate training resources and administrative support.[4;158-161] The block diagram form of the subject curriculum structure can be drawn as follows: [8; 38] (see Scheme 1):

Scheme 1

Summing up, it can be said that the subject curricula is a conceptual document of interest to students, teachers, parents and other members of the society, it covers the goals of teaching subjects and all activities to achieve these goals. This document aims to develop the skills and habits of each student, taking into account their interests and inclinations. As can be seen from the scheme we presented above, the document in question defines the main goals of education in secondary schools, general learning outcomes, content lines, learning outcomes by content lines, content standards, intra-disciplinary and interdisciplinary integration, training strategies, recommendations on training requirements, forms and methods. (these are the elements that the full contains) contains. The subject curriculum presents key learning outcomes through the interaction of content and action lines to define what students "should know" and "be able to do". [15]

The document included in the "Introduction" block (the curriculum can be interpreted as a set of documents) in any set of documents, including the curriculum, each document is an element of the whole, in addition to determining the place of any subject among the subjects taught in general education schools, as well

as the main goals of its teaching allows to define in a general way.

The "Teaching strategies" block covers the forms, methods and techniques used by the teacher in the teaching process. It should be noted that until this time, this concept was not used in the pedagogical literature of Azerbaijan. However, recently, during the period of educational reform, the concept of "educational strategy" has started to be applied when preparing subject curricula. [5; 280]

Developing the concept of learning strategies in new subject curricula and using it more effectively in organizing the pedagogical process requires, first of all, an explanation of education as one of the main pedagogical concepts in terms of modern requirements. The "Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Education" states that education is the process of systematized (according to the interests of the state, society, individual) knowledge, skills, habits and its result. [2;6]. Scientific sources emphasize that education should be treated not only as a result or just a process, but as a way of expression with broader shades of meaning. "Especially the personality-oriented nature of education requires to approach it from several positions: education is a value;

education is a system; education is a process; education is the result". [13; 115]. We completely agree with this idea.

First of all, education is viewed as a value that includes language, mentality, national skills and traditions. In the formation of these values, personality orientation, culture, collectivism, systematicity, and integrity act as leading principles. Education, which has its own system, exists in stages. These stages, which differ in their expected results, complement each other and form a general system of education by being sequentially arranged. At this time, democratization, humanization, differentiation, individualization, socialization, diversity and inclusiveness play a key role as leading principles. Education is also treated as a process, since it continuously encompasses the acquisition of universal and national values in the process of socialization. Its didactic basis is relevance to nature, practicality, directionality, variability, gradation, consideration of individual needs and continuity. Education is viewed as a result, as it is the conclusion of teacher and student activities as a whole. It is evaluated as the end of a whole step-by-step process. [5; 280]

Among the elements contained in the "Teaching strategies" block, "Description of the main requirements for the organization of subject training" has a special place. It is necessary to follow important requirements - didactic principles in the proper construction of the pedagogical process. In the organization of the pedagogical process in accordance with the currently applied curricula in the general education system, it is considered necessary to take principles such as 1) completeness of the pedagogical process, 2) creation of equal opportunities in training, 3) student-orientedness, 4) development-orientedness, 5) stimulation of activity, 6) creation of a supportive environment.

We consider it acceptable to give the following interpretation to the listed principles: based on the completeness of the pedagogical process, in the pedagogical process, the educational goals are implemented in a complex manner (developmental, educational, educative), teacher and student activities that are realized with real results are covered; In education, the same learning conditions are created for all students with equal opportunities, and the pedagogical process is regulated taking into account their potential opportunities; In the case of student-centeredness, the student is at the center of the pedagogical process, the teaching and learning work of which is aimed at satisfying the interests and needs of students, developing their talents and abilities, potential opportunities; With development orientation, students' cognitive activity is monitored, their achievements are analyzed, and the level of development of their knowledge, skills and habits is adjusted; In order to establish the pedagogical process efficiently and effectively by stimulating the activity, to increase the interest of the students in training, all the progress in their activity is evaluated, as a result, it is ensured that the students are directed to more successful learning results; Creating a supportive environment - organization of the pedagogical process on the basis of a suitable material and technical base and in a

healthy spiritual and psychological environment provides favorable and safe training conditions for the improvement of quality and efficiency. Here, we know that it is necessary to emphasize that, in addition to these principles, special methodical principles are also considered didactically important in the teaching of individual subjects.

Among the elements contained in the "Teaching strategies" block, "Teaching planning by subject" has a special place. Creating annual planning is the most important task facing educators. Planning is the direction of action of teachers to determine the main goals and achieve them. The annual planning shows when and in what order the teaching unit will be taught.

In scientific sources, it is recommended to expect the following sequence of subject planning: 1. To determine the educational units to be implemented based on the content standards; 2. Determine the principle of sequence of teaching units; 3. Allocate time according to the curriculum for each educational unit; 4. Taking into account student interests in each case. [5; 281]

The main documents used in the annual planning process are: content standards; assessment standards; education plan; textbook; methodological tool for the teacher. Let us specially emphasize that when the calendar plan is drawn up, the weeks of the school year, important events (historical days) that will take place in the school year, the name of the study units and the subjects included in them are determined. The content standards (sub-standards) to be realized through each teaching unit and topic are selected, the sources (resources) to be used are determined, and the time allocated for each topic is noted. Based on the model annual planning, the teacher individually prepares a daily or weekly lesson plan.

According to the descriptive scheme of the curriculum of the subject, in the "Education strategies" block, the "element acting as a central link" is the form and methods of training organization. Training practice has confirmed that the main organizational form of training and education work in secondary schools is the lesson. A lesson is a part or cell of the pedagogical process that has been completed to one degree or another. "The lesson is the basic movement form of training, which provides the content, principles and methods of training, is planned and regulated by the teacher within a certain time frame, and appears as a set of teacher-student relations." (academician M. Mehdizadeh).

The improvement of educational material, which contains a part of human social experience, and educational methods aimed at its mastery, conditions the modernization of their form of existence (educational material and methods for the lesson act together in the place of content) (turning into a suitable way of existence) (such is the dialectical dependence between form and content). Therefore, in addition to "traditional lesson", "modern lesson", "developing lesson", "problematic lesson", "phased lesson", "synthetic lesson", "active lesson" etc. concepts that reflect the quality characteristics of the lesson such as. The "modern lesson" model was created with intense pedagogical, psychological, and methodological research and was formed

according to the features and challenges of the era (the current century, time period).

Here, we feel it necessary to clarify some issues (in fact, they are directly - indirectly related to our research). Two stages can be conventionally distinguished in the development of new pedagogical thinking. In the course of the scientific-critical analysis of the traditional didactic system at the first stage, the optimization of the lesson was of particular importance as the main psychological and pedagogical problem. As an alternative to the traditional lesson, the meaning of the modern lesson was born at this stage. The formation of ideas about the modern lesson has been of decisive importance in the establishment of a new pedagogical thinking. Its main dimensions are reflected, first of all, in the modern lesson concept. The word "modern" in the sense of "modern lesson" has a unique heuristic meaning. "Modern lesson" does not mean "today's lesson". A lesson based on the successes of the time is called a modern lesson. In this sense, they usually distinguish two aspects that are organically connected with each other. Often, when they say modern lesson, they understand it not only to raise the scientific-theoretical level of the lesson, to modernize it. The lesson should reflect the achievements of the time according to its scientific and theoretical level. This is without a doubt. However, it would be one-sided to explain the meaning of modern lessons only in this root. We are talking about a pedagogical phenomenon. The word "modern" characterizes the lesson. This is true both from a psychological and pedagogical point of view, and from a linguistic point of view. The lesson becomes modern not only due to its scientific-theoretical level, but also due to its pedagogical concept - it is built with new dimensions of pedagogical thinking. [7; 36-37]

During the analysis of the modern lesson concept in different directions, new problems arose. One truth was already clearly understood: without rebuilding the theoretical-methodological paradigms of education with the dimensions of the time, the modernization of the lesson by itself does not give the desired effect (and could not give!).

A new (second) stage is formed in the development of new pedagogical thinking. The development of the modern education concept and the development of the modern lesson concept based on this concept constitute the main line of the second stage. Even the meanings that are particularly relevant in the first stage (for example, the activation of students' cognitive activity, etc.) sound in new meanings in the second stage. The development of theoretical thinking in students appears as an important issue and is evaluated in terms of personality.

The analysis of the materials obtained from pedagogical sources leads us to the conclusion that the use of the concept of "modern lesson" is ambiguously accepted by pedagogical researchers (theorists) and practitioners: it is more preferable to talk about the changes in the requirements for the lesson, its construction in accordance with the modern tasks of the school, and the use of appropriate terminology. is given.

The lesson as an organizational form of training is still being effectively studied, its types and structure are

being specified, the theory and practice of organization and management of the training material at the level that can play the role of the form of procedural movement is being worked out, in short, this problem has an eternal nature. We share the claim that the optimality of the structure of the lesson mainly depends on the consideration of the following factors: a) the content of the training material; b) didactic goals and tasks; c) methods and tasks of training; ç) age and personal characteristics of students; d) level of students' ability to learn.

The attitude of the student to the content and tools of the training material can be manifested as stationary or problematic. Therefore, depending on the stationarity or problem, the student's thought process is reproductive or productive. In the forms of organization of training, the content of the training material and the methods of action adequate to it appear in the place of the content. Therefore, the substructures of the forms of organization of training and their relationship remain in the monopoly of the relationship between the student's analytical and heuristic activities. The basis of the pedagogical (external), mental (internal) and methodical inter-structural relations of the organizational form is also the relation between the students' analytical and heuristic activities. The relationship between the degree of pedagogical influence in the training process and the student's internal activity and independence reflects the nature of his (student's) activity. At present, the approach to this process as a field of activity aimed at developing the human personality has begun to dominate. This did not remain unaffected by the forms of education, views on its organization, and directions for improvement. In our modern time, the idea of active (interactive) learning has gained a superior position due to the above-mentioned effects. By the way, let's emphasize that "modern lesson" is used as a synonym for the concept of "active lesson", which is an organizational form of active (interactive) training.

Training according to the demands of the 20th century is expressed as the concept of "active (interactive) training" by most theoretical pedagogues-scientists, methodologists, teachers, and other educational workers. (We had to come to this conclusion while examining scientific sources, pedagogical literature, talking with representatives of the pedagogical community).

The paradigms of the lesson, which is the organizational form of that model (the way of implementing education), are: approach to students as subjects; dialogic approach; existentiality (consideration of the integrity of human nature); integrativeness; providing a developmental character; formation of pedagogical personnel at a level that meets modern requirements; the fundamentality of the teaching-learning process: the nature of training is "subject-subject" ("S-S"); activity of the participants during the whole lesson; creation of a problem situation at the beginning of the lesson and directing its progress to the solution of the problem; conducting the lesson in the form of research; directing students to independent discovery of new knowledge through thought-provoking and guiding questions; conducting the lesson in the form of dialogue; regular existence of mutual cooperation and feedback between

teachers and students; wide use of group work, joint activity of students; diversity and innovation of learning tools and tasks; use of worksheets; creative application of knowledge, etc.

A lesson based on the listed paradigms is considered a "modern lesson". The mentioned characteristics of training (related to its organization) bring a number of advantages to it: In this process, students get the opportunity to think independently and draw conclusions freely; During the whole process, students' cognitive activity is ensured; Students have the opportunity to absorb more information in less time; Research habits are formed and developed in students; Cooperation and mutual respect is formed between students, between students and teachers.

The four main mechanisms of active (interactive) training (creating a problem situation; the student standing as a researcher, the teacher as a facilitator, a guide; the need for dialogue and cooperation; psychological support: respect and trust for the student's personality) lead to the formation of cognitive activity in students and its maintenance throughout the process. happens. As a result of activation of thinking in the process of understanding and assimilation of knowledge,

students have freedom, an opportunity for more independent perception of knowledge, and training becomes more efficient. Mechanisms of active (interactive) training ensure implementation of standards. [15]

Among the elements included in the structure of the lesson, which is the main organizational form of active (interactive) training, are: motivation (posing a problem, putting forward hypotheses); conducting research (searching for facts to test hypotheses); information exchange (presentation of obtained data and student research); discussion and organization of information (discussion of obtained information, connection of various facts, their systematization); generalization and drawing conclusions (generalizations, comparison of results with hypotheses and conclusion about their confirmation or refutation, answer to the research question); productive (creative) application (application in new conditions, solving practical problems); evaluation or reflection (inspection and evaluation of personal performance – this can be done at any stage).

The results to be achieved according to the stages of the active lesson (which these stages create the structure of the lesson) are as follows: (see table 1)

Table 1.

Stages of an active lesson	The result
1. Motivation	Research question and hypotheses
2. Conducting research	Research works, new facts
3. Information exchange	New information for discussion
4. Information discussion and organization	Systematized information
5. Summarizing and drawing conclusions	Acquired knowledge (generalization)
6. Productive (creative) application	Ways of applying knowledge and experience
7. Evaluation or reflection	The habit of evaluation, mastering the rules of learning, the habit of independent learning

The structure of the active lesson reminds of the stages of the research process (the main shade of the learning process is research). In an active lesson, new information is obtained through the student himself (as a result of research). The stage of application in an active lesson is creative in nature. One of the special stages of the active lesson is the reflection stage. As a result of reflection, the student understands the main stages of his research activity.

Learning success is determined not only by the student's ability to learn, overall abilities, etc., but also by learning motivation. In other words, for him to "read well", along with all other conditions, it is necessary to form learning motivation. The student himself, in the words of the famous English psychologist G. Eysenck, should want to read and be interested in the lesson. In school experience, there are many gifted students who simply cannot read well due to lack of motivation. G. Eysenck figuratively explained this issue as follows: "If we can bring the horse to the water trough, we can send the child to school in the same way. However, just as we cannot force a horse to drink water, we cannot force a child to read if he does not want it." For teachers, this problem - the problem of "finding the language" of the student is "Hamlet's dilemma". The effectiveness of the training process and, of course, the success of the training directly depends on its solution. Teachers already encounter this "Hamlet dilemma" step by step in their

practice. Unfortunately, it is often solved not by effective psychological methods, but by "power methods". What has been said requires that the motivation phase of the lesson (in general, learning motivation) be kept in focus. The continuity of the student's cognitive activity during the entire learning process is determined by the level at which this stage is established. [7; 160-168]

Motivation is an important component in an active lesson - it is a process that activates the thinking process and stimulates the cognitive activity of students. The existence of this process is determined by components such as goal, need, personal meaning, motive.

The motivation phase consists of the following parts: A question or task is formulated to pose the problem; Questions are suggested; Assumptions are made.

Among the factors that create motivation are the following: the problem situation that creates various hypotheses; properties of the object (unusuality, free thinking and interest-generating feature); availability of research opportunities; the possibility of creativity.[10;258] Motivation is mainly based on two principles: 1) problematic; 2) purposefulness. Motivation should be consistent with the learning outcomes of the lesson. Before building the motivation, "Substandards" and then "Learning outcomes of the lesson" should be defined. The research question arises as a result of the motivation. Motivation can be short and gradual. A

short motivation consists of only one research question. Staged motivation includes at least two stages.

Guiding questions, tasks are focused on learning outcomes, influencing factors are further strengthened for students to become active carriers of the lesson. To formulate a research question, the teacher must first identify the summary at the end of the lesson. The motivation phase ends with the hypotheses put forward according to the research question. It is important to return to it at the end of the lesson. As a result of motivation, the research question should serve the learning outcomes. In this process, the topic of the lesson plays only the role of a tool. Although the topic is a tool, in certain cases it can influence the content of the motivation.

The work plan for creating motivation is as follows: 1. Determine the subject of the lesson; 2. Draw attention to the expected learning outcomes of the lesson; 3. To honestly (determine) what conclusions (generalizations) students will come to at the end of the lesson; 4. In accordance with the results of the lesson, define and express the research question correctly (taking into account the students' level of understanding); 5. Tasks for creating a problem situation - questions, issues, studies, etc. to prepare.

In scientific sources [15], it is emphasized that all possible ways of creating motivation are divided into three main groups, which we also appreciate this consideration: interpretation of symbolic (symbolic) material (when the teacher presents this material, the teacher offers students to answer the following questions: "What does this mean?", "How does this relate to the topic we are studying?"); encouragement to ask questions.

According to our opinion, it is useful to use 3 types of questions that make thinking more relevant: 1. Questions that determine unknown issues on the studied topic - "What do we know and what do we not know about....?". During the questioning, the teacher directs the students' thinking to the right direction with the help of facilitation. After the questions have been asked, they select and separate the ones that are suitable for the research being conducted. All that is left to the teacher is to direct the students to express the question more honestly in order to clarify the research question; 2. Open questions (questions with two or more answer options) are used; 3. Questions related to the studied topic are asked with the help of keywords (keywords - properties, characteristics, function, types, types, role, importance, cause, result, connection, interaction, defect and advantage, structure, rule, etc.); 4. Solving the problem in different ways (for example, classifying it in different ways, successfully solving the problem in different ways, etc.).

The following criteria are used to evaluate motivation: appropriateness of motivation; the emergence of problems and various hypotheses as a result of motivation; brevity of motivation, implementation in a short time; that the teacher spends little time and effort on its preparation; understanding by children with moderate difficulty (taking into account their age and knowledge level).

The worksheet is a tool that organizes and directs students' research work during the implementation of active (interactive) training. The problem given to small groups and the results of its solution are reflected in the worksheet. It is useful to follow the following tips and recommendations for preparing the worksheet: 1. Specifying the purpose of the lesson: The purpose should be related to the topic and content of the lesson, "What knowledge, skills and habits should be formed?" - it should be adequate to answer the question; 2. Choosing different types of tasks (Tasks should be chosen according to the purpose of the lesson and should be aimed at solving the research problem (according to the type of thinking, according to the sources of information, according to the form of presenting the results, etc.). They should correspond to the age, knowledge and intellectual level, abilities and interests of the students. and should be differentiated in nature; should be based on the State program and national values; should be relevant, related to real life and students' experiences); 4. To use different sources of information. 5. The forms of presentation of results should be different (schemes, pictures, studies, projects, abstracts, cross-words, etc.). 6. Tasks should be clearly stated. The layout of the worksheet should be neat, concise, and visual.

During the preparation of worksheets, the scope of the task, the amount of questions, types, and presentation rules should be in focus. The worksheet must have the following requirements: It must have an attractive content and layout; The requirement, the assignment should be clear and specific; It should be suitable for children's level; It should be relevant to the purpose of the lesson.

The purpose of "Information exchange", one of the concluding stages of the active lesson, is to familiarize all students with new facts and findings. Information sharing can only be effective if the class is focused on active listening and feedback.

The purpose of the "Discussion and organization of information" stage is to systematize knowledge based on new facts and reveal the main relationship to find an answer to the research question. It is clear that the material that the teacher has to work with is detailed. He must try to connect these scattered facts to discover the main unifying idea and pattern. In that time period, comparison, analysis and synthesis are used. "How to group all these facts?" - in order for the students to be able to answer the question, the teacher should be able to imagine in advance how information can be compared, organized and reconstructed, with the help of which criteria. Let us emphasize that the choice here depends on the content of the material and the purpose of the research.

"Deriving conclusions, justifying generalization" is one of the structural elements of the lesson. After generalization, the idea formed should be compared with the research question (Does it answer this question?) and with the initial hypotheses (Are any of these correct?).

In the application of subject curricula, daily planning for each active lesson system is also an element to be focused on. It is useful to include the following in

the daily planning: Determine the expected results of the lesson (determine the learning results of the lesson based on the sub-standard); Determine what conclusions (generalizations) the students will reach at the end of the lesson; Preparing the motivation of the lesson (creating a problem situation, choosing the type of motivation, setting the research question correctly); Identify sources of knowledge used to collect new knowledge during research; Develop research tasks that can lead to the specified expected results; Determine research methods; Prepare the necessary materials and worksheets, determine the presentation form of the research; Articulating guiding questions used during discussion; Systematization of information (scheme, formula, graph, table, project, etc.); Prepare additional information, tasks, taking into account the assumed new results; Determine the time for each phase of the lesson; Preparing tasks for the creative application phase of the lesson; Choosing the evaluation form (method), defining the criteria; Determine the course of reflection based on the needs of teachers and students; Determine the technical means to be used in the lesson; Prepare stationery to be used in the lesson.

One of the important elements of the "learning strategies" system is the learning method. Despite the fact that a clear understanding of the concept of "teaching method" and the discovery of its essence have important theoretical and practical importance, debates among didacts in this direction have been ongoing for a long time. [11] In our opinion, the training method is a system of rules aimed at solving the educational, educational and developmental tasks set in the training process, determined by the principles derived from the regularities of training, and ensuring the dialectical unity of the activities of teachers and students (a component of the training process).

Presentations known to us from pedagogical sources about the nomenclature and classification of training methods (which differ in their nature and characteristics): 1. Traditional classification of training methods; 2. Classification of methods according to the training tasks performed; 3. Classification of methods according to the type (character) of cognitive activity; 4. Classification of methods according to training objectives; 5. Classification of methods according to the function of educational-cognitive activity; 6. Classification of methods according to their general characteristics; 7. Polynar classification of training methods; 8. Classification of training methods according to the main stages of training; 9. Classification of interactive training methods.

In the real pedagogical process, it is more important what methods the teacher chooses and can benefit from it to the maximum. Five general conditions should be expected when choosing training methods (this is our subjective conclusion obtained from many years of pedagogical experience and methodical sources): The goals and objectives of the training; Laws and principles of training; Learning opportunities of schoolchildren (age, level of preparation, characteristics of class staff); External conditions (geographic environment, production environment); The ability of the

teacher (experience, level of preparation, knowledge of typical situations of the educational process).

As the methods are different, there are also different conditions for their application. In addition to the variety of methods and conditions, there are random (unknown) causes in the real process. It is difficult to predict the quantity of these causes and the direction of influence. Therefore, it is necessary to choose training methods that provide the highest effectiveness in training under the current conditions. This requires mastery. An important indicator is the promotion of students to the position of researchers.

The document containing the interpretation of the content standards is one of the important elements included in the "Teaching strategies" block. Scientific sources emphasize that the content standard is the requirement set by the state for the level of knowledge and skills of the student. [5;468] The subject standards cover the content that is important for all students within the secondary education course, describe the students' comprehension abilities, knowledge and skills, determine the issues that every student in the country can and should study in the subject, and prepare students for the next level of secondary education.

The new approach to setting the content of the standards envisages that each standard consists of several defined objectives (sub-standards) and is repeated throughout the grades in an appropriately expanding capacity.

The content standards of this or that subject are systematized by classes and represented along the content line. The objective of each standard includes several expected learning outcomes defined according to the primary, secondary and upper secondary levels of education. A balance of abilities such as basic computational and procedural skills, cognitive understanding, and problem solving is expected when setting standards. These three components of the teaching and mastering of the relevant subject are not isolated from each other, they must be connected to each other and complement each other.

The function of the core standard is to explain the defined learning outcomes in a general way along the content lines. It is related to the functions of sub-standards: it creates a reliable basis for the precise determination of learning objectives; plays an important role in the correct selection of training strategies; ensures integration in training; ensures continuous development of training content; provides summative assessment for classes and subjects.

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the research work. 1. The importance of the application of the "system-structure" approach method, formed as an important branch of the dialectic regarding the discovery of the essence of the subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods, was brought to the attention of researchers; 2. The solution of one of the cognitive issues that determines the solution to the problem of revealing the essence of the subject curriculum and its application in the optimal version at the general education level - the interpretation of the elements of the "Educational strategies

block" based on the "system-structure" approach" was presented.

Practical significance of the research work. We hope that the solution of one of the important cognitive issues that determine the solution to the problem of uncovering the essence of this or that subject curriculum applied at the general education level and its application in the optimal version - the presentation of the "interpretation of the elements of the educational strategies block" based on the "system-structural" approach" It will have a positive effect on the formation of the environment of elimination of mistakes manifested in the activities of educators in the application of the subject curriculum.

The result. 1. The level of understanding of any real existence (objective existence) has a determining effect on the results of taking advantage of it in adequate directions; 2. Making mistakes in the activities of educators in the application of any subject curriculum at the general education level has a negative effect on the efficiency level of the teaching process of this subject; 3. In the process of using the curriculum of the subject, the basis of the mistakes manifested in the activity of the practical educators is based not only on one of the reasons, but also on the insufficient honest understanding of its essence by these subjects; 4. "System-structure" approach is the most reliable dialectical method of understanding any existing thing, getting to its essence; 5. The dialectical method of "system-structure" approach regarding the discovery of the essence of the subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods was not used in theoretical and technological directions; 6. One of the cognitive issues aimed at solving the problem that creates the basis for the manifestations of the error caused by the "gap" regarding the discovery of the essence of the subject curriculum and determining the ways of its application is "Interpretation of the "Elements of the Educational Strategies Block" of the subject curriculum at the general education level based on the "system-structural" approach" and Our presented research summary benefits the teaching process of this or that subject.

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